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Are Maxwell's equations intimately related to the quantum vacuum?

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Around the middle of the 19th century many of the basic laws of electromagnetism had been discovered but there was a problem: Ampère's law about how moving charges create a magnetic field, described this properly only when the electrical currents were stationary. The Scottish genius James Clerk Maxwell then postulated that an electric field introduced a current even in the vacuum and added the so-called displacement current to Ampère's law. He thus unified electricity and magnetism combining the laws of Coulomb (or Gauss), Faraday and Ampère, which is closely related to the law by Biot and Savart. For Maxwell this displacement current was a current in the ether, the medium whose physical nature had yet to be identified, the oscillation of which was thought to allow light to propagate. Later Michelson and Morley tried to measure the motion of the Earth through the ubiquitous ether using an interferometer invented for the purpose – but no motion could be detected. This led Lorentz to postulate that when moving relative to the ether, the Galilei transformation had to be replaced by the famous transformation named after him. This established that the ether was invariant under Lorentz transformation. Only when Einstein derived the Lorentz transformation by simply assuming that the speed of light is the same in all non-accelerated coordinate frames, the ether was abandoned and the vacuum was considered void¹. However, with the advent of quantum physics, with Dirac's postulation of antimatter and its subsequent discovery, the vacuum was no longer considered empty. Today we think that the vacuum is filled with polarizable virtual particle – anti-particle pairs. In the past, several authors already remarked that the vacuum is like a dielectric [see [1] for details] and that one might think of it as a modern Lorentz-invariant quantum ether. This allows e. g. for a simple phenomenological derivation of the Schwinger limit, the electric field strength at which the vacuum breaks down forming an electron-positron plasma. The argument is as follows:

According to the energy-time uncertainty relation, virtual pairs can be considered real in time windows shorter than Planck's constant divided by the restmass energy of the pair, or equivalently, using

the position-momentum uncertainty, in regions of space smaller than $\Delta x \leq \hbar/mc$. An external electric field E will

exert a force eE to each particle. The energy this force can transfer to the particle is limited by the available acceleration distance Δx . If the electric field is so high that within the available distance it will acquire a kinetic energy equal to its rest mass, then it may become real: $eE\Delta x = mc^2$. Solving for E yields the Schwinger-Sauter limit, $E_s = m^2 c^3 / (e\hbar)$.

This encourages one to think about the link of Maxwell's equations to the quantum vacuum with its virtual elementary particles and anti-particles. In the equation for matter, $\vec{D} = \epsilon_0 \vec{E} + \vec{P}$, the displacement in the vacuum appears as the first term on the right hand side, where ϵ_0 is the permittivity of the vacuum, \vec{E} the electric field and \vec{P} the polarization of real matter. The term $\epsilon_0 \vec{E}$ should then be the polarization of the vacuum, proportional to \vec{E} , hence the linear response of the vacuum². While one finds statements in the literature, that the term $\epsilon_0 \vec{E}$ is the contribution of the vacuum, nobody calculated the response of the vacuum before we did in 2010 [see ref in 1]. Looking through the literature, searching for what authors of text books wrote about the displacement, one finds that most of them do not make any special remark, with two exceptions: One is Edward W. Purcell, Nobel laureate and author of the seminal Berkeley Physics Course volume 2, who mentions the displacement \vec{D} 'a bit grudgingly', as he writes himself, adding that "We have mentioned D because it is hallowed by tradition, beginning with Maxwell, and the student is sure to encounter it in other books, many of which treat it with more respect than it deserves." [pages 381-382]. The other one is Igor E. Tamm, likewise Nobel laureate and author of the book "Fundamentals of the Theory of Electricity", who writes (in the English translation): "The electric displacement vector is in essence the sum of two absolutely different physical quantities: the field intensity and (multiplied by 4π) the polarization of a unit volume of the medium. Nevertheless, the introduction of this vector enormously simplifies the studying of the field in dielectrics." [page 117]. He uses Gaussian units, in which case \vec{E} and \vec{P} have the same dimension, which triggered his remark. In SI units the factor ϵ_0 in front of \vec{E} indicates that the term is more than just the electric field. Igor Tamm might well appreciate the interpretation of this term as being the polarization of the vacuum.

'Encouraged' by these statements we calculated the polarization of the vacuum in the same way as one would calculate that of a dielectric crystal in solid state physics. Recognizing that \vec{D} is a dipole moment density, the path we should take was clear. First calculate the (virtual) dipole moment of an electron – positron pair induced by an electric field and then divide by the volume it occupies. The first step seemed ob-

¹ When we shared our thoughts with John Weiner, he recalled that the Michelson-Morley experiment is usually taken as an evidence that the ether concept is useless when trying to understand the experimental results. And with a twinkle in his eye, he pointed out that it is well known that if you show that 'something' is useless, this does not prove that this 'something' does not exist. We parted with the happy thought that there is room for a modern ether. (Note, that Einstein's relationship with the ether was complex, and changed over time.)

² Note, that one commonly finds the statement that while there is nonlinear, there is no linear response of the vacuum. We argue that there is linear response but it is already built into Maxwell's equations which are postulated axiomatically in QED, so that there is no linear response of the vacuum beyond the one already accounted for in Maxwell's equations.

vious: the energy gap between the two lowest energy states starting from the Dirac sea, $2m_{\text{electron}}c_{\text{rel}}^2$, gives you a spring constant, which in turn yields the charge displacement for a given electric field. The force on the charges is given by Lorentz, and against this force works the action of the ‘very stiff rest mass spring’. This approach was motivated by the experience that any physical system operating close to a point of equilibrium can be modelled as a harmonic oscillator.

The latest improvement came from treating each particle – anti-particle pair as a 3D quantum harmonic oscillator [1]. Note, that we assume we do not know the speed of light at this point, but we know the limiting speed c_{rel} , as it appears in Lorentz’s transformation and in Einstein’s relation between energy and mass. Calculating ϵ_0 and μ_0 then implies that we also calculate the speed of light which will later be compared to c_{rel} . But how to determine the volume a pair occupies? Back in 2009 we asked Joseph H. Eberly of Rochester University, who suggested we talk to one of his former post-docs, the late Nikolay B. Narozhny from Moscow Engineering Physics Institute. He said what we wanted to do is strange, but if we wanted to finish the calculation, he advised us to take the cube of the Compton wavelength of the electron as the volume occupied by a virtual electron-positron pair. Incidentally and not surprisingly the extension of the ground state wave function of the quantum harmonic oscillator is also of that order. So this provides a ball park number but not a precise value for the volume per pair as it does in the case of a dielectric crystal. Using the Compton wavelength cubed gave a value for ϵ_0 , which was only about twenty times too small. We were all excited because we could come as close as this to the correct value. When we showed this to Joe Eberly, he asked: “Where is the mass of the electron?”. We explained that as both the induced dipole moment and the Compton volume scaled as the inverse of the electron mass cubed, the mass drops out and the result depends only on the square of the electron charge. He then remarked, that if this is true, the other electrically charged elementary particles should contribute in the same way despite of their higher mass and one would have to sum over all these elementary particles. That struck us because with the known different types of elementary particles in the standard model one gains a factor of 9, coming indeed to within a factor of two to the experimentally known value of ϵ_0 . At that point we were even more excited. In the latest version [1] we get

$$\epsilon_0 = \frac{e^2}{2c_{\text{rel}}\hbar} \sum_i^{\text{el. par.}} \frac{q_i^2 \hbar^3 / (m_i c_{\text{rel}})^3}{e^2 V_i}$$

and

$$\frac{1}{\mu_0} = \frac{e^2 c_{\text{rel}}}{2\hbar} \sum_i^{\text{el. par.}} \frac{q_i^2 \hbar^3 / (m_i c_{\text{rel}})^3}{e^2 V_i}$$

The uncertainty in these formulae concerns (1) how many types of elementary charged particles have to be summed over, and (2) which is the ‘unit cell’ volume V_i occupied by the pair with index ‘i’. Luckily these uncertain terms cancel when multiplying ϵ_0 and μ_0 to calculate the speed of light and we get $c = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}} = c_{\text{rel}}$, a very satisfying result!

In quantum optics, the models we use are often not Lorentz-invariant. Such a model is not appropriate for a vacuum without any induced structure. Although there are energy gaps $2m_i c^2$, the vacuum as a dielectric should not be dis-

persive when interacting with a plane wave in the sense that all its properties should be Lorentz-invariant. Regarding dispersion, this means that there cannot be a dependence on ω , only a dependence on the squared modulus of the wave vector in four dimensions (four-vector), $k^2 = \vec{k}^2 - (\omega^2/c^2)$. Therefore, the permittivity of the vacuum cannot depend on ω , but it can depend on $\sqrt{k^2 c^2}$. For propagating photons one always finds $\sqrt{k^2 c^2} = 0$. It is, however, possible to have $\sqrt{k^2 c^2} > 0$ in the case of non-propagating photons, as in the ‘near-field’ close to a sub-wavelength antenna, or the photons exchanged between charged particles conveying the Coulomb force between them. In particle physics one refers to ‘off the mass-shell contributions’ when dealing with $\sqrt{k^2 c^2} > 0$, leading e.g. to the running of the fine structure constant in collisions with high momentum exchange. The running fine structure constant calculated in quantum field theory (QFT) relates to a running ϵ_0 , according to $\alpha(k^2) = e^2 / (4\pi\epsilon_0(k^2)\hbar c)$. The above term for ϵ_0 can be shown to compare favorably well with the running fine structure constant [1].

Surprisingly our phenomenological derivation does not involve any divergence, as it does in quantum field theory. So, what is wrong? At some point, Massimo Altarelli told us that identifying the cube of the Compton wavelength with the volume occupied by a virtual particle – anti-particle pair is not convincing to him. He suggested trying a different approach: to count, in a somewhat larger box of volume V , the number of standing wave modes of the matter wave of one particular elementary particle, each associated with a particular momentum vector $\hbar\vec{k}$ – but of course this number diverges as $|\hbar\vec{k}|^2$ goes to infinity, leading to zero volume per pair. This is finally similar to the divergencies encountered in Standard QFT. In the early days of QFT, the simplest way to deal with such divergencies was to introduce a relativistic momentum cut-off. A cut-off near $|\vec{p}| = |\hbar\vec{k}| = mc$ led e. g. to a good result for the Lamb shift of hydrogen. Here, the same cut-off leads to a volume per wave-particle mode which is about the Compton wavelength cubed, coinciding with the advice received from Nikolay Narozhny. In this derivation one uses plane waves for the particle wave and not spatially confined wave functions as in the harmonic oscillator model above. There are speculations, that some of the divergencies in QFT might be the result of using a cumbersome basis for the matter wave functions [2,3]. It would be interesting to explore this further.

At the end of all this, we are looking back with awe at the seminal achievements of James Clerk Maxwell. He unified electricity and magnetism with his equations. They were not only Lorentz invariant long before first George Francis FitzGerald and then Hendrik Antoon Lorentz dealt with the correct transformation valid also for relativistic speeds; they do not only correctly describe the spatio-temporal mode functions of the light field in which the quantum optical excitations live; but on top of all this, the numerical values of the parameters in Maxwell’s equations are closely linked to the properties of the modern quantum vacuum filled with virtual elementary particles of different types!

[1] G. Leuchs, M. Hawton and L.L. Sánchez-Soto, *Physics* **5**, 179 (2023)
 [2] H. M. Fried and Y. Gabellini, *Annals of Physics* **327**, 1645 (2012)
 [3] G. Scharf, *Finite Quantum Electrodynamics*, Springer Verlag, Berlin Heidelberg 1989